

FORMATION OF MUSIC HEARING SKILLS IN PRIMARY GRADE STUDENTS

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Annotation: This thesis discusses the content, purpose and pedagogical significance of the formation of music listening skills in primary school students on a scientific and theoretical basis. The need to form aesthetic taste, emotional perception, ability to distinguish melody and rhythm, and skills to analyze a listened musical work through listening is substantiated. The thesis shows the methodology for the gradual development of music listening skills, the structure of the lesson process focused on listening activities, the role of interactive methods and the individual approach of the teacher as an important factor.

Keywords: music listening, aesthetic education, listening competence, musical perception, methodology, interactive approach, musical thinking, listening activities.

Introduction

Today, ensuring the comprehensive development of the individual in the educational process, especially the formation of aesthetic, emotional and cultural-intellectual competencies, is considered one of the urgent issues. The foundation of such competencies is laid at the preschool and primary education stages. In particular, through the teaching of music in primary grades, students develop such skills and competencies as musical culture, musical perception, emotional sensitivity, rhythmic perception, listening comprehension and musical thinking.

The age-related psychophysiological characteristics of the development of primary school students are characterized by the active formation of their auditory perception, emotional sensitivity and artistic and aesthetic taste. Therefore, it is at this stage that the formation of the ability to listen to music is an important component of education. Listening to music is not just listening, but the process of consciously perceiving a certain musical work, understanding its ideological and artistic content, feeling musical images, distinguishing the structural elements of music - pitch, rhythm, dynamics, timbre, form. This requires didactic and methodological approaches, as well as an age-appropriate psychopedagogical process.

In modern pedagogy, the competence of listening to music is considered as a complex system of skills that serves to develop the student's general musical

literacy, creative thinking and aesthetic taste. To form this competence, interactive methods, multimedia tools, musical and pedagogical technologies, as well as lesson content based on modern methodological concepts are necessary. In particular, when choosing musical listening materials, attention should be paid to the harmony of age characteristics, samples of national and world musical heritage.

Also, in the formation of musical aural skills in primary school students, the teacher's musical and pedagogical skills, an approach based on professional competence, a person-oriented educational strategy and the ability to create an emotional climate play an important role. The thesis aims to analyze these factors from a scientific-theoretical and practical-methodological point of view, as well as to substantiate effective mechanisms for the formation of musical aural skills. The formation of musical aural skills in primary school students is a multi-component pedagogical process that simultaneously affects the psychomotor, affective and cognitive development of students. This process includes such processes as creating emotional resonance through listening to music, perceiving a musical image, understanding the aesthetic idea in the work, understanding rhythm and pitch structures, distinguishing timbres and analyzing elements of musical form through hearing.

The following main methodological approaches were used in the study:

Cognitive approach - developing students' conscious perception of musical material, learning through listening, and musical thinking;

Activity-based approach - organizing music listening as an active process, in which the student becomes not just a passive listener, but a subject analyzing music and working with images;

Competency-based approach - serving the individual development of the student by forming general, subject-specific, and person-oriented competencies in music listening.

During the study, primary school music lessons in several secondary schools in the Khorezm region were observed, the effectiveness of musical listening exercises was evaluated, and the students' listening activity, emotional responses, and level of musical literacy were diagnosed. For this purpose, the following methods were used:

Pedagogical observation - assessing students' listening activity, emotional participation, and motivation during the lesson;

Tests - measuring the level of ability to identify rhythm, pitch, tempo, dynamics and images in a piece of music listened to by listening to it;

Interviews and questionnaires - determining the existing methods of listening to music and their effectiveness through interviews with teachers and students.

The results of the analysis showed that the successful formation of the skill of listening to music depends on a number of important conditions:

Methodological support - age-appropriateness of the listening materials used in the lessons, harmonious selection of samples from national and world music, the level of imagery and pedagogical orientation of the musical work;

Professional competence of the teacher - theoretical knowledge of music pedagogy, skills in the effective use of psychological approaches and interactive methods;

Communicative environment - creating an emotional and aesthetic climate in the lesson that stimulates students' listening activity and allows them to freely express their thoughts;

Expanding the experience of musical hearing through the use of technological tools - audiovisual tools, music applications, virtual symphonic libraries.

Practical exercises conducted on the basis of this systematic approach served the gradual development of musical hearing competence in students. The results of the experiment showed that methodologically correctly organized musical hearing exercises effectively form musical taste, auditory perception and emotional sensitivity in students.

Music is a type of art that directly affects the human soul, awakens subtle feelings in it and encourages a sense of beauty. In particular, the role of music in shaping a person's aesthetic attitude to life is incomparable. From this point of view, developing a primary school student's musical perception, forming his or her ability to hear music means not only imparting musical knowledge, but also arming the child with an aesthetic consciousness.

Primary school students have a sensitive, emotionally open and lively perception of music. They perceive music not only as a set of sounds, but also as a figurative, emotional reality. Therefore, the process of listening to music becomes an important psycho-pedagogical tool in the formation of a student's personality. In this process, the role of the teacher is not only as a giver of knowledge, but also as a guide, arousing aesthetic feelings, inspiring musical thinking.

In particular, the formation of auditory activity should not be limited to just listening to music. This activity includes complex cognitive processes such as

understanding and analyzing music, emotional perception of images in it, sensing the structure of a musical work, understanding rhythmic and melodic changes, discovering the author's idea through musical means. Therefore, the skill of listening to music requires a specific methodological approach, systematic training and a deep understanding of child psychology.

It is important that in this activity the student should be formed not as a passive listener, but as an active observer, questioner and person who seeks to understand the inner logic of musical expression. This serves as the basis for the competence of musical listening. In this process, the teacher enters into dialogue with the students, poses aesthetic questions around each musical work heard, encourages children to observe, express their feelings, and express figurative thoughts based on musical images.

In addition, the use of interactive methods in organizing listening activities (clustering, games such as "musical associations", "listen-find", integration with fine arts) creates a basis for greater understanding and comprehension of music. In particular, through the use of multimedia tools and visual images, musical hearing and imagination are combined. This leads to the strengthening of emotional images in the child along with musical perception.

Conclusion.

Based on the results of the above analysis and research, the formation of musical hearing skills in primary school students leads to the following conclusions:

The ability to listen to music is a complex psycho-pedagogical activity that is formed as a result of the student's not only listening to a musical work, but also perceiving it emotionally, cognitively and intellectually. This skill is a key factor in the development of musical literacy and aesthetic taste.

The primary school period is the most favorable and effective age stage for the formation of musical listening skills, and this process is combined with the intensive development of children's auditory perception, emotional sensitivity and imagination.

Cognitive, activity-based, competency-based and person-oriented approaches play an important role in the formation of musical listening competence. Through these approaches, students not only hear music, but also analyze it, feel it and express their personal aesthetic attitude.

The study found that the main conditions for developing musical listening skills are: methodologically well-organized lesson content, selection of age-appropriate musical works, professional and methodological training of the

teacher, use of interactive methods, creation of an aesthetic environment that paves the way for active observation by students.

The effectiveness of musical listening activities is significantly increased through the use of multimedia tools, integrative approaches and creative tasks. This allows for more meaningful, interesting and effective organization of music lessons.

The staged methodological model developed on the basis of the study - preparatory, cognitive-analytical and reflexive creative stages - serves the systematic development of musical listening skills and can be effectively implemented in primary education practice.

In conclusion, it can be said that the formation of musical listening skills in the primary education system is an urgent and necessary pedagogical task that forms not only musical perception in students, but also an aesthetic attitude to art, life and beauty in general. Scientific and methodological research and approaches enriched with experience in this area will raise the quality of music education to a new level.

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